

Some Neglected Empirical Regularities in Long Run Stock Price Behaviour

Rajas Parchure¹ & Surender Kaur²

Abstract: The study attempts to examine previously unexplored long-run stock price behaviours, focusing on the convergence of stock returns over extended periods and the relationship between earnings fluctuations and stock prices. Using data from 2006 to 2024 across major indices in India, Japan, the UK, the USA, and the Eurozone, the paper analyses “running returns” and “holding period returns.” It finds that long-term holding returns provide a more stable measure of performance compared to short-term running returns, with significant convergence of returns and a very clear link between earnings growth and price appreciation over longer durations. The paper challenges traditional financial theories like CAPM and the Efficient Market Hypothesis, advocating for the inclusion of these long-term trends in investment strategies and theoretical finance. Documenting these long-term trends, the study enriches our understanding of stock market behaviour over longer periods and offers insights that could impact both theoretical finance and practical investment strategies. The research gives insights for the integration of these long-term empirical regularities into decision-making frameworks for investors.

Keywords: Equity premium puzzle, relationship between returns and earnings, long-term stock price behaviour.

1. Introduction

The study of stock price dynamics has traditionally focused on short-term i.e. day-on-day, week-on-week, month-on-month returns, and so on. This feature has obscured some interesting phenomena that are revealed in the behaviour of stock returns when they are measured over longer intervals of time like year-on-year, five-year on five-year returns and so on. The purpose of this paper is to call the attention of the readers to two empirical phenomena that are revealed in data on long-term cumulative returns. a) the relatively rapid convergence between the returns on stocks towards one another, a phenomenon that is not emphasized in the literature because the majority of studies of stock market behaviour used short-term running returns and b) the significantly greater strength of the relationship between long-run earnings

¹ Reserve Bank of India, Professor of Finance, Gokhale Institute of Politics and Economics, Pune

² Research Scholar (Gokhale Institute of Politics and Economics) – 411004

growth/decline and long-run stock price appreciation/depreciation as compared to the relationship between the short-run earnings growth/decline and short-run stock price appreciation/depreciation.

2. Literature Review

The history of finance theory within economics is relatively recent. Although credit markets have long been integral to economic activities, the initial theories about financial markets were primarily intuitive and developed by practitioners. Louis Bachelier's groundbreaking work in 1900 was initially neglected by both theorists and investors. Economists such as Henry C. Emery (1896), Irving Fisher (1906, 1907, 1930), and John Maynard Keynes (1930, 1936) contributed significantly to understanding credit markets and the function of risk in speculation. Nevertheless, many people still saw financial markets more as speculative pursuits than as legitimate economic mechanisms, a view exemplified by Keynes' "beauty contest" analogy. Keynes' idea of "normal backwardation" (1923, 1930), later expanded by John Hicks (1939) and Nicholas Kaldor (1939), explored the operation of futures markets, laying the foundation for future empirical studies. The advent of Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) by Harry Markowitz (1952, 1959) and James Tobin's (1958) work on risk-free assets dramatically altered investment approaches through diversification. William Sharpe (1964) and John Lintner (1965) introduced the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM), which further simplified portfolio choices and made them more computationally manageable for practitioners. However, Richard Roll's critiques (1977, 1978) of CAPM led to alternatives like Robert Merton's (1973) Intertemporal CAPM (ICAPM) and Stephen Ross's (1976) Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT). Empirical research has also been vital in elucidating stock market behaviour. Notable studies by Holbrook Working (1934), Alfred Cowles (1933, 1937), and Maurice Kendall (1953) found that asset prices often follow a random walk, opposing traditional notions of price forecast ability. The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH), developed by Paul Samuelson (1965) and Eugene Fama (1970), asserted that markets rapidly integrate all available information, thus making consistent excess returns challenging to achieve.

Yet, theorists like Robert Shiller (1981), Sanford Grossman and Joseph Stiglitz (1980), and Paul Milgrom and Nancy Stokey (1982) questioned EMH's theoretical robustness, especially regarding information asymmetry and speculative bubbles. Malkiel (1998) critically assessed stock return predictability, indicating that empirical evidence of short-term momentum and long-run mean reversion questions the concept of strict market efficiency. His research showed that certain financial ratios (e.g., P/E, P/B, and size factors) have some ability to predict stock returns, in agreement with findings on long-term earnings-stock return correlations. However, he cautioned that survivorship bias and data mining could amplify these conclusions. Malkiel further pointed out that mutual fund performance studies often exaggerate

success due to sample selection biases, a concern that also applies when probing long-term return stability. These foundational theories and empirical discoveries establish a framework for understanding long-term stock price behaviour. The research gap is most of the literature focuses on short term returns(daily, monthly or weekly) while long term returns are relatively unexplored, models like CAPM, EMH and APT focus primarily on short term efficiency and risk premia with- out adequately addressing long-term empirical regularities and in this study extends these works by examining empirical regularities in long-term return convergence and the earnings-stock price relationship across multiple markets over an extended period.

3. Methodology

This research employs quarterly stock price and earnings data encompassing the period from 2006 to 2024 across five principal stock markets: India (BSE 500), Japan (Nikkei 250), the United Kingdom (FTSE All-Share), the United States (S&P 500), and the Eurozone (STOXX). The data were obtained from Thomson Reuters (Eikon) and CMIE (Prowess) for India. In the next section approaches to return measurement are employed in this study.

Short Term and Long-term Stock Return Measurement

Before proceeding to elaborate on the individual exercises it is necessary to point out a difference in the formula for the stock return usually employed in the stock market literature and long-term returns employed here and the relation between the two. The usual formula is:

$$r_t = \left(\frac{S_t + D_t}{S_{t-1}} \right) - 1 \quad (1)$$

Wherever relevant, D_t , the dividend paid by the stock in period t is added to S_t . This return may be called the “running return” in which the size of the investment is revised period by period. In contrast the “holding return” is defined as,

$$R_t = \left(\frac{S_t}{S_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{t}} - 1 \quad (2)$$

in which the base period investment is kept fixed. This may be called the “holding return over period t ” or in short, holding return. There is of course an obvious connection between the running returns and holding return over the period $(0, N)$. The running returns r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n and the holding returns R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n are connected by the formulae.

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_1 &= r_1 \\
 R_2 &= [(1 + r_1)(1 + r_2)]^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \\
 R_n &= \prod_{t=1}^n (1 + r_t)^{\frac{1}{n}} - 1
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

so that R_t the holding returns up to period N are the geometric means of the running returns over the same period. Obviously, the arithmetic mean of the running returns $r_n = \sum r_t / N$ always exceeds the geometric mean R_N which is invariably implied in Modern Portfolio Theory, whose behaviour is being explained in this paper. Even though the respective rates of return namely running returns and holding period returns are intimately related to one another, it is the purpose of this paper to show that there are concrete empirical regularities captured by holding period returns but not revealed by running returns. Moreover, these empirical regularities hold across several stock markets.

4. Empirical Examination of Stock returns Convergence

In this section, we shall explore the behaviour exhibited by stock returns over long periods of time. We shall consider both types of returns: running returns and holding returns, as defined by equations 1 and 2, respectively. For this study, we have analysed data from five countries: India (BSE500), Japan (Nikkei 250), the UK (FTSE All-Share), the USA (S&P 500), and the Eurozone (STOXX). The timeframe considered for this study spans from 2006 to 2024, with quarterly data sourced from Thomson Reuters (Eikon) and CMIE. Wherever there was missing data in the sample, we resorted to interpolating the data. The sample for the study consists of companies drawn from leading stock indices across these five countries. Therefore, the final sample includes 163 companies from India, 142 from Japan, 233 from the UK, 221 from the USA, and 227 from the Eurozone.

Figure A: India running returns

Figure B: India holding period returns

Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness	Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
15Q	0.0946	0.0675	0.3145	6.8163	1.2168	15Q	0.2488	0.2155	0.2574	8.7048	2.1083
30Q	0.0766	0.0442	0.2649	8.6672	1.4716	3Q	0.2113	0.1926	0.1619	2.3710	1.2544
44Q	0.0745	0.0458	0.2403	10.5793	1.5987	44Q	0.2232	0.2035	0.1373	0.5634	0.8038
58Q	0.0679	0.0428	0.2311	10.1965	1.4651	58Q	0.1971	0.1873	0.1196	0.7087	0.7438
72Q	0.0645	0.0407	0.2211	10.3751	1.4722	72Q	0.1879	0.1793	0.0871	0.4191	0.7051

Table A: Descriptive Statistics

Table B: Descriptive Statistics

Figure C: Japan running returns

Figure D: Japan holding period returns

Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness	Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
15Q	-0.0139	-0.0262	0.1749	6.2609	0.9151	15Q	-0.1054	-0.1257	0.1000	3.2375	1.1590
30Q	0.0206	0.0077	0.1605	6.0005	0.7974	30Q	0.0369	0.0155	0.0900	6.3850	1.9405
44Q	0.0294	0.0187	0.1549	6.3754	0.7467	44Q	0.0768	0.0679	0.0800	2.7411	1.1557
58Q	0.0264	0.0179	0.1528	5.9471	0.6631	58Q	0.0652	0.0551	0.0800	2.8421	1.2178
72Q	0.0247	0.0164	0.1477	5.8818	0.6361	72Q	0.0592	0.0536	0.0500	4.7658	1.4677

Table C: Descriptive Statistics

Table D: Descriptive Statistics

Figure E: UK running returns

Figure F: UK holding period returns

Note: The data sources for all the tables and graphs presented are Thomson Reuters Eikon. For data specific to India, the source is Prowess CMIE

Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
15Q	0.0094	0.0001	0.1925	8.63	1.14
30Q	0.0241	0.0217	0.1669	11.82	1.26
44Q	0.0246	0.0225	0.1505	12.99	1.22
58Q	0.0246	0.0235	0.1556	11.92	1.03
72Q	0.0198	0.0189	0.1504	11.43	0.98

Table E: Descriptive Statistics

Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
15Q	-0.0228	-0.0255	0.1454	1.20	-0.63
30Q	0.0471	0.0421	0.0857	3.25	-0.65
44Q	0.0585	0.0645	0.0771	2.43	-0.46
58Q	0.0541	0.0596	0.0738	1.32	-0.13
72Q	0.0367	0.0423	0.0601	1.20	-0.29

Table F: Descriptive Statistics

Figure G: USA running returns

Figure H: USA holding period returns

Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness	Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
15Q	0.0181	0.0208	0.1644	1.62	0.15	15Q	0.0237	0.0088	0.1201	11.34	2.37
30Q	0.0343	0.0391	0.1421	2.57	0.04	30Q	0.1027	0.0859	0.0809	6.53	1.78
44Q	0.0345	0.0370	0.1286	3.02	0.06	44Q	0.1108	0.1036	0.0654	4.52	1.34
58Q	0.0371	0.0397	0.1322	3.07	0.08	58Q	0.1203	0.1159	0.0669	1.80	0.85
72Q	0.0337	0.0359	0.1315	2.56	0.08	72Q	0.1056	0.1000	0.0604	1.81	0.88

Table G: Descriptive Statistics

Table H: Descriptive Statistics

Figure I: Eurozone running returns

Figure J: Eurozone holding period returns

Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness	Time frame	Mean	Median	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
15Q	0.0090	-0.0009	0.1806	5.94	0.98	15Q	-0.0208	-0.0283	0.1113	0.37	0.21
30Q	0.0240	0.0219	0.1530	5.95	0.67	30Q	0.0538	0.0464	0.0768	0.32	0.17
44Q	0.0287	0.0260	0.1424	5.07	0.45	44Q	0.0737	0.0673	0.0688	0.27	0.27
58Q	0.0287	0.0260	0.1424	5.07	0.45	58Q	0.0793	0.0744	0.0742	0.52	0.43
72Q	0.0251	0.0226	0.1409	4.40	0.41	72Q	0.0641	0.0563	0.0595	0.68	0.71

Table I: Descriptive Statistics

Table J: Descriptive statistics

Tables A to J describe the manner in which the parameters of the probability distributions of the running returns and holding period returns change as the holding period increases from 15Q (3.75 years) to 72Q (18 years). Notably, the standard deviation of holding period returns which measures the cross-sectional

variation of individual stocks from the sample mean declines at a much faster rate than that of running returns.

This pattern holds true across all markets included in the study. Similar trends are observed for other moments of the distribution, i.e., skewness and kurtosis. A decline in skewness implies that extremely high rates of return become less probable, while extremely low rates of return become more probable as the holding period increases. Skewness declines more sharply for holding period returns than for running returns. Kurtosis consistently increases when holding period returns are considered, but it may either rise or decline for running returns (see Table I for the Eurozone).

The convergence of stock returns towards uniformity indicated by declines in the cross-sectional standard deviation of individual stocks in the samples across countries over long periods of time is scarcely mentioned in the literature on stock market behaviour, which is instead dominated by the idea of random walks. Obviously, no attention is given to the systematic behaviour of the higher moments of the statistical distributions, such as skewness and kurtosis. The modal probability of earning the mean rate of return increases as the holding period lengthens, simply because higher order moments tend to disappear in normal or lognormal distributions, which are customarily assumed in the literature.

5. Relationship between Earnings and Stock Returns

In this section, we consider the elementary relationship between the rate of growth of earnings per share and the rate of stock price appreciation, as understood from fundamental analysis.

Cross-Sectional Regression Models

We estimate two separate cross-sectional regression models: one for running returns and another for holding period returns (HPR), both regressed on earnings per share (EPS) growth rate across different quarter groups.

Regression 1: Running Returns on EPS growth rate

For each quarter group q the model is specified as:

$$r_{i,q} = \alpha_q + \beta_q \cdot EPSG_{i,q} + \epsilon_{i,q} \quad (4)$$

where: In the regression models, $r_{i,q}$ represents the Running Return of firm i in quarter group q . The

intercept for each quarter group is denoted as α_q , while β_q represents the coefficient measuring the sensitivity of Running Returns to EPS Growth. The Earnings Per Share Growth Rate of firm i in quarter group q is denoted as $EPSG_{i,q}$ (for both running and holding price returns), and $\epsilon_{i,q}$ is the error term associated with firm i in quarter group q .

Regression 2: Holding Period Returns vs. EPS Growth Rate

Similarly, for each quarter group q

$$R_{i,q} = \alpha_q + \beta_q \cdot EPSG_{i,q} + \epsilon_{i,q} \quad (5)$$

General Model Representation

If we extend the model across multiple quarter groups, we can summarize the regression models as:

$$r_{i,q} = \alpha_q + \beta_q \cdot EPSG_{i,q} + \epsilon_{i,q} \quad (6)$$

$$R_{i,q} = \alpha_q + \beta_q \cdot EPSG_{i,q} + \epsilon_{i,q} \quad (7)$$

Each quarter group q has its own regression coefficients, allowing for an analysis of how the relationship between stock returns and earnings growth evolves over different periods.

Country	Parameters	15Q	30Q	40Q	58Q	720Q
		0.0631 (2.2312)	0.0446 (3.1681)	0.0352 (3.4863)	0.0439 (4.9455)	0.0398 (5.5129)
	α					
		0.3684 (4.2773)	0.3063 (6.0042)	0.2900 (7.2222)	0.2403 (6.5238)	0.2347 (7.4888)
India	β					
	R-Square	0.0085	0.0081	0.0079	0.0049	0.0051
		0.0551 (4.0916)	0.0580 (6.0662)	0.0493 (7.3578)	0.0415 (8.0162)	0.0419 (9.4919)
	α					
		0.0336 (0.4374)	0.3301 (5.5875)	0.2806 (6.6029)	0.2490 (7.4489)	0.2495 (8.4580)
Japan	β					
	R-Square	0.0001	0.0085	0.0080	0.0077	0.0079
		0.0601 (5.0604)	0.0329 (6.1726)	0.0246 (4.8423)	-0.0052 (-1.0215)	0.0071 (0.9473)
	α					
		0.8898 (10.9981)	0.8539 (15.6434)	0.8000 (15.2460)	0.7898 (14.0580)	0.8236 (7.7335)
UK	β					
	R-Square	0.6277	0.7538	0.7453	0.7177	0.4933
		0.0427 (6.1093)	0.0428 (11.0357)	0.0396 (12.2074)	0.0448 (13.0157)	0.0443 (14.9921)
	α					
		0.0357 (0.8450)	0.0254 (0.9564)	0.0553 (2.2680)	0.0200 (0.7970)	0.0272 (1.2486)
USA	β					
	R-Square	0.0003	0.0002	0.0006	0.0001	0.0001
		0.1501 (1.3125)	0.0868 (1.5517)	0.0622 (2.1534)	0.0622 (2.1534)	0.0790 (2.3919)
	α					
		0.9026 (1.4264)	0.6501 (1.7999)	0.4252 (2.1390)	0.4252 (2.1390)	0.6338 (2.7451)
Eurozone	β					
	R-Square	0.0007	0.0005	0.0004	0.0004	0.0005

Table H: Running Regression Results

Country	Parameters	15Q	30Q	44Q	58Q	72Q
	α	0.0194 (0.6311)	-0.0189 (-0.9638)	-0.0366 (-2.2266)	-0.0039 (-0.3035)	-0.0086 (-0.5947)
India	β	0.3270 (3.8043)	0.3988 (5.4114)	0.3471 (5.5247)	0.2987 (5.3821)	0.3266 (4.6859)
	R-Square	0.0875	0.1624	0.1681	0.1610	0.1270
	α	0.1051 (5.9346)	0.0404 (6.7795)	0.0324 (6.0397)	0.0264 (5.6451)	0.0305 (7.0459)
Japan	β	1.0299 (8.3141)	0.7585 (11.8577)	0.6881 (14.1787)	0.6280 (14.1654)	0.7448 (13.6869)
	R-Square	0.3579	0.5314	0.6185	0.6181	0.6017
	α	0.0601 (5.0604)	0.0329 (6.1726)	0.0246 (4.8423)	-0.0052 (-1.0215)	0.0071 (0.9473)
UK	β	0.8898 (10.9981)	0.8539 (15.6434)	0.8000 (15.2460)	0.7898 (14.0580)	0.8236 (7.7335)
	R-Square	0.3941	0.5682	0.5555	0.5152	0.2433
	α	0.0694 (5.6936)	0.0234 (2.4562)	0.0010 (0.1276)	0.0058 (0.8516)	0.0104 (1.9956)
USA	β	0.7782 (7.7948)	0.8255 (11.3105)	0.8660 (13.6947)	0.7860 (15.8468)	0.8372 (19.5185)
	R-Square	0.2357	0.3937	0.4877	0.5604	0.6592
	α	0.0545 (5.0868)	0.0122 (2.0626)	0.0100 (2.1780)	-0.0003 (-0.0674)	0.0187 (5.5733)
Eurozone	β	0.9640 (10.1624)	0.9192 (14.5377)	0.8003 (17.4899)	0.6964 (17.3902)	0.7216 (18.7938)
	R-Square	0.3318	0.5040	0.5953	0.5925	0.6294

Table K: HPR Regression Results

Note: The numbers in parentheses represent the *t*-statistics.

It can be said with some justification that the empirical regularity explored in the earlier section has as much statistical content as economic context, to the extent that geometric means are always numerically smaller than the corresponding arithmetic means, and the standard deviations from the geometric means are always lower than those from the arithmetic means.

A more powerful test is required to demonstrate the superiority of holding returns when the objective is to understand empirical regularities in long-run stock price behaviour.

Tables J and K are arranged as follows. Each pair of tables shows the results of regressing stock price returns on the growth rate of earnings per share. For example, Table J shows the regression between running return and running earnings per share growth rate.³ Table K shows the regression between the holding period return and the growth rate of earnings per share over the corresponding holding period.⁴ This has been done for several holding periods and across all the markets included in the sample. The regression of running return on running earnings per share is shown in Equation (8), and for holding period return in Equation (9).

$$r_i = a + b g_i + u_i \quad (8)$$

$$R_i = a + b G_i + u_i \quad (9)$$

As Tables J and K show, the estimated slope parameters of the regressions are all positive. Notably, in all cases without exception, the t-values of the slope parameters for Equation 9 exceed those for Equation 8 and are greater than 2, implying that the p-values are nearly zero. Moreover, except for the case of India, the R^2 values for Equation 9 exceed those for Equation 8, indicating a greater explanatory power of earnings growth as a determinant of long-term holding returns. In addition, the R^2 values invariably increase as longer time periods are considered.

In other words, even though the running returns and holding returns are related to one another in a straightforward manner, as shown in Equation 3, the informational content they convey differs depending on the length of the time period considered.

6. Concluding Remarks

Modern theories of stock price behaviour, such as the Capital Asset Pricing Model, Arbitrage Pricing Theory, Efficient Market Hypothesis, and the Fama-French models, attempt to explain the observed behaviour of running rates of return on stocks. However, they are not necessarily concerned with long-term phenomena such as the equity premium puzzle (Prescott and Mehra, 1985), which becomes visible only in

³ r_i = running returns and g_i = running earnings per share

⁴ R_i = holding period return and G_i = growth rate of earnings per share

long-term returns. The purpose of this paper is to explore other kinds of empirical regularities exhibited by long-run stock price behaviour. We have pointed out two such regularities: (a) convergence towards uniformity of long-term stock returns, and (b) increasing explanatory power of earnings growth in determining stock returns as the holding period increases.

References

- Agwu Egbo, S. O. N., Adewole, A. P., and Maduegbuna, A. N. (2010). A random walk model for stock market prices.
- Bernstein, P. L. (2009). *Capital ideas evolving*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Campbell, J. Y. and Kyle, A. S. (1993). Smart money, noise trading and stock price behaviour. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 60(1):1–34.
- Cowle's 3rd, A. (1933). Can stock market forecasters forecast? *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, pages 309–324.
- Emm, E. E. and Trevino, R. C. (2019). Risk and investment horizon: Is time really money? *The Journal of Investing*, 28(1):86–96.
- Fama, E. F. (1965). The behavior of stock-market prices. *The Journal of Business*, 38(1):34–105.
- Fama, E. F. (1995). Random walks in stock market prices. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 51(1):75– 80.
- Fama, E. F. (1998). Market efficiency, long-term returns, and behavioral finance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 49(3):283–306.
- Godfrey, M. D., Granger, C. W. J., and Morgenstern, O. (1964). The random-walk hypothesis of stock market behavior. *Kyklos*, 17(1):1–30.
- Graham, B., Dodd, D. L. F., Cottle, S., and Tatham, C. (1951). *Security Analysis: Principles and Technique*. McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Grossman, S. J. and Stiglitz, J. E. (1980). On the impossibility of informationally efficient markets. *The American economic review*, 70(3):393–408.
- Kendall, M. G. and Hill, A. B. (1953). The analysis of economic time-series-part i: Prices. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series A (General)*, 116(1):11–34.
- Kurz, M., Jin, H., and Motolese, M. (2005). Determinants of stock market volatility and risk premia. *Annals of Finance*, 1:109–147.
- Levy, R. A. (1967). Random walks: Reality or myth. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 23(6):69–77.
- Li, B., Liu, B., Bianchi, R., and Su, J. J. (2012). Stock returns and holding periods. *JASSA*, (2):43–48.
- Malkiel, B. G. (1996). *A Random Walk Down Wall Street*. Norton, New York.

- Malkiel, B. G. (2003). The efficient market hypothesis and its critics. Journal of economic perspectives, 17(1):59–82.
- Mehra, R. and Prescott, E. C. (1985). The equity premium: A puzzle. Journal of Monetary Economics, 15(2):145–161.
- Mehra, R. and Prescott, E. C. (1988). The equity risk premium: A solution? Journal of Monetary Economics, 22(1):133–136.
- Mehra, R. and Prescott, E. C. (2003). The equity premium in retrospect, volume 1, pages 889–938. Elsevier.
- Merton, R. C. and Samuelson, P. A. (1992). Continuous-time finance.
- Prescott, E. C. and Mehra, R. (2005). Recursive competitive equilibrium: The case of homogeneous households, pages 357–371.
- Reddy, S. S. and Ram, P. R. (1996). Agricultural finance and management. CBS Publishers & Distributors Pvt Limited, India.
- Shiller, R. J. et al. (1981). Do stock prices move too much to be justified by subsequent changes in dividends?
- Working, H. (1934). A random-difference series for use in the analysis of time series. Journal of the American Statistical Association, 29(185):11–24.

Citation in APA 7th Edition:

Publisher's Note: *The views and opinions expressed in this article are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of the publisher or editorial board. The publisher assumes no responsibility for any consequences arising from the use of information contained herein.*